

Integrated Assessment of Air Pollution in Contrasting Geographies of Chile

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Introduction

Background

Air pollution in Santiago has been in the public consciousness for several decades. In 1994 CENMA took on the task of designating limit values for air quality and installing the first monitoring stations. The Ministry of Environment was created in 2011 and took over this role.

Since the beginning of the 20th century several industrial zones began to appear in coastal locations and towards the end of the century they encroached on urban areas such as Concepción and Quintero). Several episodes of acute intoxication have occurred in recent years, many affecting school children. The government and the public are now demanding better and more transparent monitoring of emissions from mining and industrial activities.

Despite the efforts of the Chilean government to improve and expand the air quality monitoring network that measures urban and industrial pollution, the air quality is not improving fast enough. There are still areas with few or no measurements despite public concern about air pollution.

Carrying out new measurements and analysing existing monitoring data all helps to inform policy and new air quality standards and outreach. The scientific community, local and national authorities, health professionals and socio-environmental organizations need to work together.

Objectives

Study how air pollution and its detailed composition varies across Chile.

Investigate how mobile measurements or short-term local measurement campaigns can fill in what is missing from the SINCA network.

Study local human exposure to air pollutants.

Understand how Chile's contrasting climate zones and local meteorology influence air quality.

Carry out measurements and run workshops with the public and create outreach materials about air quality.

The Team

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Chapter 1. The North

Calama and Alto Loa

Indigenous communities have lived sustainably in the barren, inhospitable north of Chile for centuries. The arrival of **mining activities**, particularly the extraction of copper and lithium, poses a threat to the environment and communities, but these minerals are of great global importance.

In January 2021 we took dust samples from the houses of **Alto Loa villages** and again in January 2023 we sampled dust from all the schools and kindergartens of the city of **Calama**. We were invited to help in Nicolás Zanetta's PhD field work. The results of the analysis of dust samples from Alto Loa indicated that these villages are exposed to metal contamination (e.g. As, Sb, Cd, Mo, Pb), especially those that are downwind of the mines and the tailings dam.

Preliminary results of Arsenic (As) levels in dust samples from the schools of Calama.

Wind dispersion map showing how the wind travels over the tailings toward the towns of Alto Loa.

We conducted toxicity analyses on the dust in schools, which revealed the presence of a variety of metals. It would be interesting to study cases of respiratory diseases and autism in these schools and establish a correlation between the levels of certain metals and the students' health.

Chapter 2. Central Chile

Sacrifice zones

The central part of Chile, where the majority of the country's population is concentrated, is also the region with the highest energy demand. Many petroleum products arrive in the ports and are processed in coastal industrial sectors. We studied two case studies in Quintero-Puchuncaví and in the commune of **Chacabuco**.

Atmospheric data workshop, part of a Universidad de Playa Ancha course organised for the community of Quintero.

During 2000 and 2001 researchers from the University of Toulouse carried out a study on **metal** contamination in the rural communities in the communes of Til Til, Colina and Lampa. Local people working with the researchers collected atmospheric dust and used the rootless plant, *Tillandsia bergeri* to capture the metals present in the air. We collaborated in the data analysis, which revealed the presence of several metals in both types of samples and showed that this could have an effect on the health of the local people.

Environmental education for local communities

The efforts of researchers, local authorities and local activists have been fundamental in improving environment awareness and to empower local communities living close to industrial areas. Running workshops for communities has taught them more about air quality data and trained them to assist scientists with sample collection.

Santiago

Santiago is a **city of 7 million people** and with the Andes mountains acting as a barrier, trapping pollutants such as Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), especially in winter when thermal inversions compress the atmospheric boundary layer above the city. Despite the fact that **PM_{2.5} levels have shown a significant decrease since the 1980s**, the city of Santiago still experiences pollution episodes (or Alerts) where with concentrations above 80 µg/m³.

In summer of 2023, measurements of atmospheric pollutants (SO₂, O₃, NO₂ and PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) were carried out from a family health centre in the commune of La Pintana.

We collected 34 different air samples in desorption tubes using a hand pump during my UK colleagues' research visit. The air samples were analysed in Leicester University with a gas chromatograph and they indicated the presence of 183 different organic compounds in the commune of La Pintana.

Because of Santiago's huge size, it is hard to carry out representative measurements without having dozens of instruments. However, local measurements, including capturing the air for subsequent laboratory analysis can help to improve our understanding of air pollution variability and its possible sources and effects.

The Andes Mountains

The **Center for Climate and Resilience Research (CR)2**'s Cerro Tres Puntas high altitude station consists of a hut and cutting edge meteorological instruments installed on its roof and a tall tower. It is located at **3685 m altitude**, on the edge of the Valle Nevado ski center, 60 km from Santiago. Between February and March 2025, an optical Particulate Matter instrument was installed and we managed to detect the transport of air pollution from Santiago to its neighbouring mountains.

We have 5 yeas of..

meteorological measurements at this station (temperature, precipitation, relative humidity, radiation and wind). Although we were able to measure air pollution (**PM1, PM2.5, PM10**) for a few weeks, these instruments require more power than the solar panels can provide in winter, especially when the instrument needs to heat the incoming air during low temperature conditions. We are very grateful to the company Prosamb for lending us this instrument.

Daily Particulate Matter (PM2.5) levels during the last 2 weeks of February - after noon levels rise until 16:00 or 18:00 and drop again in the evening.

Location of the station, east of Santiago and south of the Los Bronces Copper mine.

Chapter 3. The South

Coyhaique

The south of Chile also experiences harsh conditions similar to the North, but in this case, due to its cold and wet climate. The city of Coyhaique, the capital of the Aysén region, has grown significantly in recent years. The most common form of heating is with firewood and with many periods with low wind speeds in winter and being enclosed by mountains, the smoke from the stoves envelops the city practically all winter.

We have mapped the variability in air pollution in different neighbourhoods of Coyhaique by carrying out many mobile measurements with local people since we started working here in 2019. We also installed fixed PM2.5 measurements inside and outside of schools and homes.

An important milestone

In 2024 we captured the vertical variability in air pollution, using drones equipped with sensors to measure particulate matter.

We sent 2 drones up with a PM2.5 sensor (Plantower) and the results show that the densest pollution on the evening of 30th September 2024 was between 100 and 150m above the surface.

We measured inside and outside of houses in 2022 and 2024. **Fortunately, the levels of PM2.5 inside the houses were lower than outside.** We made weekly reports for each household to explain the data from their houses.

Pollution from the domestic wood burning continues to be a serious problem in the South of Chile. Although the local government is promoting stove replacement programs, there is still resistance to change, such as the cost of alternatives, poor communication and not least, a cultural dependence on firewood.

Chapter 4. Instruments

Passive collectors

Most atmospheric pollutant measurements are performed with instruments that use optical techniques or gravimetric methods (weighing the samples) to determine their concentration. The specific make-up of a sample's components can be analyzed with passive collection methods. For example, by passing air through filters, the composition of particulate matter can be analysed, and if air is collected in tubes or a cylinder, **Organic Compounds (VOCs)** can be determined.

Filters collected by an instrument that pumps air through a filter for 48 hours. Particles of size less than 2.5 μm or 10 μm (PM_{2.5} or PM₁₀) are collected on a Teflon filter for compositional analysis of metals.

This frisbee collector is left in place for 3 months so that the **polyurethane foam discs (PUF)** can capture Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and other semivolatile compounds in the air. VOCs can be measured in a Gas Chromatograph (in Leicester University) after collecting the air in desorption tubes with a hand pump.

A commercial Minivol PM collector instrument is shown in between two UDD-designed "Eolo" instruments

The results of the metals contained in the PM_{2.5} and VOC samples at various locations in Chile are very innovative and could answer more complex questions related to environmental health and toxicity. We are currently **processing the results from a Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** to group metals according to source type and toxicity.

The Chilean Monitoring Network

The **Ministry of the Environment** runs 218 **SINCA** monitoring stations that measure one or more of the pollutants PM10, PM2.5, O3, NO2, SO2 and CO.

The first stations were installed in the early 1990s and, in the last 6 years, several stations which used to be private stations run by the industries themselves have been incorporated into the SINCA network. All the stations are located in urban areas or close to industrial zones.

We studied the annual variability of MP2.5 in the 5 macrozones of Chile between 1993 and 2024. We observed a clear decrease in PM2.5, especially in winter. We analysed historical daily profiles, caused by rush hour or household stove use.

Although most of the monitoring stations show a reduction in criteria pollutants (those with a national limit value), concentrations are often still higher than the national limit values. Levels are still too high for PM2.5 in every macro-zone except the Norte Grande, but PM10 exceeds limits in the Norte Grande.

Atmospheric Decontamination Plans

Carolina Concha's Masters thesis analysed all the Atmospheric Decontamination Plans in Chile. A total of **13 of these plans** have been activated between 1996 and 2018. So far, no plan has met the goal of reducing pollution levels below the pollution limit values that it originally surpassed.

Región	PDA	Zona saturada/latente			PDA
		Contaminante	Norma	Fecha	
Antofagasta	Tocopilla	MP10	Anual	04-10-2007	12-10-2010
	Calama	MP10	Anual	30-05-2009	12-05-2022
Atacama	Hualco	MP10	Anual	23-05-2012	30-08-2017
Coquimbo	Andacollo	MP10	Diario y anual	06-04-2009	26-12-2014
Valparaíso	Concón, Quintero y Puchuncaví	MP10	Anual	09-06-2015	27-12-2018
		MP2.5	Diario		
Metropolitana	Región Metropolitana	O3, MP10, CO, NO2	8 horas y anual	01-08-1996	24-11-2017
		MP2.5	Diario	15-11-2014	
O'Higgins	Valle Central Región de O'Higgins	MP10	Diario y anual	27-03-2009	05-01-2021
		MP2.5	Diario y anual	30-05-2018	
Maule	Talca y Maule	MP10	Diario y anual	22-06-2010	28-03-2016
	Valle Central de la Provincia de Curicó	MP10	Diario	08-03-2016	20-12-2019
Ñuble	Chillán y Chillán Viejo	MP10	Diario y anual	25-03-2013	28-03-2016
		MP2.5			
Biobío	Los Angeles	MP10	Diario	11-06-2015	22-02-2017
	Concepción	MP10	Diario	25-07-2006	17-12-2019
MP2.5		Diario	14-07-2015		
Araucanía	Temuco y Padre de las Casas	MP10	Diario	11-05-2005	27-02-2015
		MP2.5	Diario	06-05-2013	
Los Ríos	Valdivia	MP10	Diario y anual	10-06-2014	23-06-2017
Los Lagos	Osorno	MP10	Diario y anual	28-11-2012	28-03-2016
		MP2.5			
Aysén	Coyhaique	MP10	Diario y anual	28-11-2012	17-07-2019
		MP2.5	Diario	30-08-2016	

Main ADPs initiatives	Quantity of Plans including these
Emission controls	16
Environmental education and outreach	16
Emission compensation	15
Management of critical episodes	12
Transportation initiatives	11
Improvement of wood quality	10
Improvement of heating devices	10
Improving thermal efficiency of homes	10
Air quality monitoring	2
Creation of green areas and cycle paths	2
Controlled Outdoor burning bans	1
Dust control	1

The table shows how many Decontamination Plans include each main initiative.

A **cost-benefit** analysis of each initiative should be considered. For example, the key benefits of improving people's health is incredibly important, it has a cost but it also would save money in the long term if people are healthier.

Chapter 5: Outreach

Outreach was an important part of this project. We ran workshops with the community (in Alto Loa, Chacabuco, Coyhaique and Quintero) as well as hands-on activities in schools. We created several educational videos for the public to explain air pollution, the root of the socio-environmental issues in Chile and also provide a glimpse into the motivations of environmental scientists. We also organised events, contributed to articles in the press and on our local university website and social media.

[Día Internacional del Aire Limpio por un Cielo Azul](#)

Chapter 5: Outreach

Chile: Torn between Natural Abundance and Uncontrolled Extractivism

Economic Development and environmental problems

Air Pollution: A multi-faceted problem

Instruments for measuring air pollution

Community, research and the Science's role

Conversations about air quality.

Documentary about measurements with the drone in Coyhaique

"Un triángulo de incertidumbre": revelan una poca conocida zona de sacrificio en el norte de Santiago.

Con taller de ciencia ciudadana e interpretación de datos culmina curso sobre calidad del aire en Quintero y Puchuncaví

Although the workshops and activities' main focus was to disseminate information about air quality, it was interesting how it is nigh on impossible to not bring up other environmental issues. We realized how important it is to address socio-environmental issues and make people feel like they are intrinsically part of the environment and have a responsibility for protecting it.

Chapter 6 – Future work

Over the course of these 3 years, we made some important advances, thanks to the collaboration between several universities and organizations. Working on a local level you note the varied social, environmental, cultural and economic situations. Our research and the application of new measurement techniques needs to be adapted to these local conditions for us to be able to propose useful solutions.

Our initial analyses of **Chile's monitoring network** and Atmospheric Decontamination Plans suggests that current policies are not as effective as they could be. We hope to be able to analyse this in a global context and suggest sustainable strategies for air quality issues in Chile.

The impact of air pollution on **health** has been touched upon in several of the studies in this project thanks to collaborations with new colleagues. We can see many opportunities to deepen this line of work with epidemiologists and also by exploring more about the oxidative potential of particulate matter.

Being a Principal investigator for the CITEC Millennium Nucleus has opened up the possibility of developing training activities in the use of low-cost sensors and passive collection **for community science projects**. We can help communities to better measure pollution and climate and therefore better understand and care for their local environment.

There are many **instruments** that we still want to characterise and use more efficiently. We have lots of plans for the new PM collectors (Eolos) and our portable PM sensors and we want to try out the cylinder air capture system. We need to develop new **calibration protocols** for the PM, NO₂, CO, SO₂ and O₃ reference instruments.

In 2025 and 2026 we will be installing PM, NO₂, NO, CO, SO₂, O₃, CO₂, total VOC, meteorology stations and Dust collectors for the "**Public Environmental Baseline**" project with the Ministry of Environment. We will install several stations in remote locations of the Metropolitan Region.

From 2025 onwards...

Carlos Manzano's new FONDECYT Regular 1251574 project (with Zoe as co-researcher), will test **air pollution passive collection methods**.

Reflections

I also wanted to reflect upon on the impact of the project on the people involved in this research. It takes time to build a strong team; there are ups and downs, successes and failures, moments of intense creativity and the challenges that come from integrating an interdisciplinary team. More than ten universities collaborated in this project; both public and private (a new concept to understand for a British researcher), public agencies, companies and independent researchers.

The very ambitious objectives of this project have been humbling and we now see that it is impossible to achieve everything planned in this limited time period. Part of the process has been recognizing that achieving certain results requires more time, and you cannot hurry the data analysis. We are still on the long journey of writing up the scientific papers that this work deserves.

This research has been challenging and a continuous learning process, especially when inserting ourselves into the local realities in the field. We have to learn to listen to and develop a relationship with the local residents who expect clear answers from our research. These results have to be put in a local, regional, national and global context and it is part of our responsibility to explain our research carefully and communicate it well so that it has a greater impact and improves our understanding of the environment and our impact on it.

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Nicolás Zanetta-Colombo, PhD Universitat Heidelberg (2024): **Metalscapes: How mining has shaped metal(loid) distribution in the Atacama Desert?**

Carolina Concha, Magister de Ciencias de la Ingeniería, UDD (2024): **Planes de Descontaminación Atmosférica en Chile: Evaluación de impacto, atribuciones y tendencias**

Hector Matus, Magister en Química, Universidad de Chile (2025): **Potencial oxidativo de muestras ambientales recolectadas mediante captadores pasivos**

**INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT
OF AIR POLLUTION IN CONTRASTING
GEOGRAPHIES OF CHILE**

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